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ESSENTIAL OIL PRESERVATIVES WITH TIMOL

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named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Annotation: In medicine, treatment of a certain disease and this disease. Plants used for prevention are called medicinal plants is called. Medicinal for the treatment and prevention of diseases. Medicinal plants are prepared from plants or they are medicinal preparations and pure medicinal substances are obtained. For this plants have biological properties to treat diseases from the parts rich in active substances, that is, from the underground organs of some plants (root, rhizome, tuber or onions), and some from above-ground organs (leaf, flower, fruit, the entire above-ground part of a seed, bark, or herb) is used. Sometimes types of medicine, medicinal preparation and pure substances through primary processing of plants and animals extracted essential oils, resins, oils and fats, tree resins, poisons (snake and bee venom), lanolin, propolis and it is also prepared and obtained from others.

Keywords: plants, preparation, drug, organs, animals, water, extract, sodium, chemical.

Thymol is a colorless, characteristic aromatic, large and clear crystal, well soluble in alcohol and ether, poorly soluble in vinegar. With alkaline solutions, it forms thymolate, a phenolate-type compound that is well soluble in water.

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Thymol is extracted from the essential oil by the following method: adding a 5 percent sodium alkali solution to the essential oil and shaking it. In this case, thymol forms a thymol compound of the phenolate type and dissolves into the water layer. After the mixture is cooled, the water layer is separated from the oil layer and treated with acid to release thymol, which is then recrystallized and purified.

Usage. Thymol is used in medicine to disinfect the mucous membrane of the mouth and relieve toothache, as well as in the treatment of skin diseases. In addition to these, the worm also has the property of driving. It is mainly used in gelatin capsules to drive hookworms and hookworms. After consuming the Thymol drug, the patient is given saline rinses.

AJGON FRUIT AND OIL - FRUCTUS ET OLEUM AJOWAN1

The name of the plant. Ajgon (Zirai carmon) — *Trachyspermum ammi* (L.) Sprague. (*Carum ajowan* Benth. et Hook.); belongs to the family of celery - Apiaceae (umbelliferae - Umbelliferae). It is an annual herb growing to 40-60 cm in height. The stem is upright, branched from the base, multifaceted. The leaf is simple, divided twice or three times (the leaf blade is linear), and the sheath is arranged in a row on the stem. The flowers are small, white or light purple, collected in a complex umbrella. The compound umbrella roll and the simple umbrella roll are composed of linear petals. The flowers have calyx and petals and 5 stamens, the maternal node is two-digit, located below. The fruit is a double pistachio. It blooms in June-July, the fruit ripens in August-September.

Geographic distribution. Homeland India. It is grown in the republics of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. Product preparation. The product is harvested similar to fennel fruit. Appearance of the product. The finished product consists of elongated ovoid, gray-green or brown double pistachios. The length of

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the fruit is 2.5-4 mm, the width is 1.8-2 mm, and it is easily divided into two parts. Each fruit half is round on the outside and flat on the inside, with 5 ribs. The smell of the product is pleasant and it has a spicy taste. Only essential oil is extracted from Ajgon fruit.

Chemical composition. Ajgon fruit contains 2-11% essential oil, 25-32% fat, 15-17% protein. The essential oil is extracted from the ripe and crushed fruit using steam. It is a colorless, yellow or brown liquid with a tangy odor and a pungent taste. Density 0.897-0.916, refractive index 1.496-1.504. Essential oil contains 40-60 percent phenols (thymol and partially carvacrol), as well as pinene, terpinene, phellandrene, simol and other compounds.

Usage. Thymol is mainly extracted from the essential oil of ajgon. After removing thymol from the essential oil, the remaining part - thymen, is used to make toothpaste and soaps because it has antiseptic properties. A medicinal preparation. Thymol (thymol is released in a gelatin capsule).

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